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Confronting (Post)-War Precariousness and Precarity: Socialist Yugoslav Literature for Children

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Abstract

In this article I examine how literature for children re-established itself in the socially, economically, and institutionally devastated and nascent revolutionary precarious situation of the post-war period. I draw on a larger study of socialist Yugoslav literature for children (1945–91) and with reference to the first post-WWII issues of the Slovenian children's magazines *Ciciban* (1945–present) and *Pionir* (1945–90). I also explore how the emergent literature for children, particularly magazines, addressed a generation who had experienced violence, persecution, orphanhood, flight, internment, famine, occupation, and armed resistance, followed by post-war daily life. I draw on the concepts of 'precariousness' and 'precarity' (Butler) in the sense of an insecure existential state and the conditions for it. Instead of a top-down approach derived from totalitarianism research (usually employed in the examination of immediate post-war socialist production), a bottom-up approach that considers the complex relationships between (cultural)-political, (infra)structural, material, interpersonal, and affective contexts (as well as the historical objectifications that are embodied in the post-war production for children discussed here) allows a consideration of the past in a more complex light. It also highlights the overdue need for discussion on how to approach the topic of war with children in times of 'more or less permanent war' (Butler).

Key words: children in war, precariousness, (post-)war literature for children, institutional forms, war trauma, socialist Yugoslavia (1945–91)

The post-Yugoslav wars (1991–2001) with their brutal culmination in the Srebrenica/Potočari massacre (11–19 July 1995, the first genocide in Europe after WWII) finalised the dissolution

of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (1945–91)¹ and affected the whole post-Yugoslav region profoundly. Nevertheless, in recent children's literature of the post-Yugoslav countries one searches almost in vain for depictions of children in war. By contrast, in the period of socialist Yugoslavia in all the nationally fragmented (though ideologically and structurally connected) Yugoslav children's literatures,² the experience of war was one of the most common motifs. Children's literatures of the different Yugoslav national production contexts were not only interlinked linguistically³ but were also the subject of intense cultural-political, editorial, translational, institutional, professional, and academic exchange. Especially prominent in all Yugoslav children's literature was the motif of the organised armed resistance by the *Narodnoosvobodilna vojska* (NOV) [People's Liberation Army], 1941–5, against the Fascist and Nazi occupying forces and their collaborators during WWII. In addition, the war and the subsequent socialist revolution marked these literatures profoundly in their institutional, production, and formal modes. These phenomena have especially in recent scholarship been interpreted as a trend arising from rigid political control bordering on totalitarianism. Putting into operation the concepts of 'precariousness' as an insecure existential state and 'precarity' as the conditions inducing such a state (Butler), in this article I first raise the question of the institutional modes of Yugoslav post-war literature for children. Secondly, drawing on the hermeneutic (Meretoja) and relational (Feldmann and Laub) understandings of trauma, which highlight the social act of discursivation of trauma as a potential means of the overcoming traumatic experiences, I examine how these magazines addressed children in their experiences of war and of the post-war reality.

Why should we concern ourselves today with socialist Yugoslav literature for children as well as its war images and interpellations of children? Researchers from different fields of studies have identified (with regard to changes in how childhood has been re-scripted in the post-socialist shifts)⁴ the rise of romanticised ideas of childhood, in which children are constructed as socially undefined and idealised (Ule; Spaskovska; Burcar). While in the socialist modernist teleology children were seen as 'a symbolic representative of societal change' and as such embodied a capacity for societal agency, in contemporary times children represent an age group 'which has no particular or significant social importance' (Ule 29). Lilijana Burcar, a researcher in English literature, childhood, and socialist studies, writes:

the ideology of innocent childhood fails to recognise that the child is itself a subject, that it is therefore always historically specific and culturally and spatially situated in terms of physical and psychological modality. Therefore, the reintroduction of the romantic imagining of innocent childhood, which posits the child as transcendental, that is to say beyond the reach of time and social currents, is a particular kind of political category. For it is not only the understanding that the child is also the bearer of a flexible subjectivity that is constantly becoming the focus of discourse that is being erased at the turn of the 21st century, but also the revival of conservative views on gender, identity and so on, that are quietly taking place in the background of the re-emergence of the romantic icon. (2)

The romanticised portrayal of children as excluded from social life and citizenship has consequences not only in the subjectivation of children, who are expected to repeat learned, often oppressive conventions. The conservative ideology of childhood is a political category (Burcar), as it supports political discourse and a social order in which the rights of children and women especially, but also of other demographic groups, are being eroded. Thus, childhood politics need to be considered in a larger framework – not only together with gender politics but also within a broader context of power and governance.

Let's Talk about Children!

The romanticised childhood has, especially in the last three post-socialist decades, often served as a foil to socialist childhood experiences and their portrayals in literature for children (including schoolbooks) or socialist education. In her analysis of the graphic dimension of the children's magazine *Ciciban*, Petra Černe Oven observes in the post-war issues 'a strong political orientation: the images are full of red stars, real-socialist iconography, partisans, pioneers and labour actions' (6). Ildiko Erdei sees in socialist education an 'explicit political disposition' with the aim to control 'in a manner and to a degree incomparable with any other previous historical period' (156). Radina Vučetić misses in the socialist Yugoslav ABC books 'universal values such as love for one's family, friendship, and real relations with society' (251). 'These textbooks', Vučetić claims,

produced propaganda about life in a happy socialist society, but at the same time, they showed children that they should take part in the building of such a society. [...] As the greatest, and practically only values, Tito, the National Liberation Struggle, the homeland, the army, national heroes, reconstruction and building, working campaigns, as well as membership in, and loyalty to, the pioneers' organisation were imposed. (251)

Why, then, should socialist Yugoslav post-war literature for children be re-examined if neither the dominance of the social realism (and also partly of the socialist realism)⁵ nor the presence of these motifs from Yugoslav history can be denied? As I hope to show, a re-reading of socialist Yugoslav post-war production for children, through the concepts of 'precariousness' and 'precarity', will help in not only understanding the Yugoslav revolutionary period in a more nuanced way but also work towards restoring an understanding of children as inherently socialised beings. In addition, by studying socialist Yugoslav literature for children, and its portrayals of them, we can indeed learn some lessons on agency, regarding the producers of children's print and how they can support children in their efforts to confront the difficulties and devastation of war.

Judith Butler's *Precarious Life: The Powers of Mourning and Violence* and *Frames of War: When Is Life Grievable?* are two collections of essays on contemporary 'more or less permanent war' (*Precarious Life* xix), in which Butler considers, starting from an ontological and existential perspective, the conditions in which 'specific lives cannot be apprehended as injured or lost' as they are not 'apprehended as living' (*Frames of War* 1); thus, they are made precarious. She promotes a 'new bodily ontology' through rethinking 'precariousness, vulnerability, injurability, interdependency, exposure, bodily persistence, desire, work and the claims of language and social belonging' (*Frames of War* 2). Precarity, however, 'designates that politically induced condition which produces and sharpens the precariousness of life (especially of certain populations), which become differentially exposed to injury, violence, and death' (*Frames of War* 25). In Butler's proposal of 'precarity', the concept of a subordinating power resonates: an ideological, institutional, and material authority producing the framework for an insecure existential state or 'precariousness' of life. Referring to this twofold concept, I propose a reconsideration of whether the Yugoslav post-war state's organisation of institutional modes of literature for children added to the unquestionable post-war precariousness – regarding both the producers and their public, children. For the sake of brevity, I focus on a single case: that of Ljubljana-based Mladinska knjiga in Slovenia, the publisher of the magazines *Ciciban* and *Pionir*. However, due to the centralised federal framework of the post-war years, the following findings are also applicable to other Yugoslav production contexts of the time (Tropin and Barač). In the concluding part of the article, I discuss the post-war issues of

these magazines with regard to their representations of the 'precariousness' of life, of children's war and post-war experiences and trauma. According to the hermeneutic model, that which is traumatic is considered to be the experience of extreme or also continuous violence that 'severely diminishes one's sense of agency, self-worth and possibilities to act in the world' (Meretoja 34). However, if trauma is recounted, heard, and, as such, socially recognised then it may be overcome (Feldmann and Laub). Comparativist Hanna Meretoja in addition highlights the impact of literature, the arts, and social movements, which can provide vocabularies for coping with traumatic experiences (31).

Institutional Modes of Publishing for Children

Aware that children constituted almost one half of the Yugoslav post-war population (Petrović Todosijević 157, 158, according to the Statistical Yearbook for FNRJ [Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia] for the year 1954), Yugoslav revolutionaries, in order to counter the brutal WWII Nazi and Fascist violence and achieve the subsequent socialist renewal of society, needed to address children specifically. Hitherto a relatively unimportant societal group, children became the subject of active social protection (Jeraj 'Otroci socializma') and political subjectivation, especially through the promotion and implementation of political agitation and education.⁶ The social homogenisation of children was organised initially after the Soviet model of Pioneer organisation. After the war, all schoolchildren became members of the Pioneer organisation, to the extent that the word 'pioneer' became in socialist Yugoslavia a synonym for schoolchild. The organisation promoted the educational premise of pioneers as 'honest, sincere, considerate, meticulous, knowledgeable, generous' (Čerin in Duda 59). However, children were already being actively addressed by the socialist movement before and during the war (Duda). The involvement of children in the resistance during WWII was co-ordinated by the regionally run *Zveze mladine* [Leagues of Youth], which addressed children also via printed magazines in the liberated territories; in Slovenia this was the magazine *Slovenski pionir* (1943–5) with its regional versions (Vošnjak 30).⁷ Mitja Vošnjak, who acted as the first editor of the magazine, recollected its editorial politics as follows:

it was a question of deciding whether to start publishing a pioneers' newspaper focusing on quality reading, which children always need, or to choose the format of a newsletter, which would inform on and explain events, and above all mobilise young people to take an even more active part in the general revolutionary efforts of the popular masses. In the extraordinary circumstances of the occupation, or rather of the birth of the new people's power, in the circumstances of the inexorable struggle for freedom and the mobilisation of the entire revolutionary potential, we took a decision which corresponded to the particular objective conditions: namely, that *Slovenski pionir* should not only be the political bulletin of the Slovene pioneers, but also culturally edited and written, which would in particular ensure the subsequent participation of the ranks of important cultural workers. (31)

The post-war precariousness was marked by institutional devastation due to various factors. Pre-war and wartime Fascist⁸ and Nazi oppression had included redundancies, persecution, imprisonment, internment, murder, and the burning of books in the South-Slavic languages. The NOB had instituted *kulturni molk* [cultural silence] as a resistance strategy, and the post-war period featured the prohibition of private publishers. Finally, there was a lack of material (paper, inks, printing machines and similar). In this precarious situation, literature for children, with its cultural-political orientation and organisational structures, was embedded into a political context, concisely described by Aleš Gabrič with the term *agitpropovska kulturna politika* (agitprop cultural policy). In his study of the wartime cultural-political discourses

within the Slovene NOB (Osvobodilna fronta [Liberation Front]) and the post-war (1945–52) cultural-political and organisational structures in the realm of education and culture, of which literature and printing were a part, Gabrič described a centralised decision-making and capillary implementation system. The agitprop of the Centralni komite Komunistične partije Jugoslavije [Central Committee of the Communist Party of Yugoslavia] encompassed sections for print and agitation, theory-lecturing, culture, pedagogy, and an organisational-technical section. The agitprops of all levels of the Communist party (from federal, republic, city to local) and of different field organisations⁹ were structured after the manner of the federal party agitprop, to which they were also subordinated, and they oversaw questions of print, education, and culture (Gabrič 494–503). Thus, the agitprop of the League of Slovenian Youth took over the re-establishment of publishing for children in Slovenia (Štraus), taking its lead from the NOB-authored 1945 document *Vprašanje organizacije našega tiska in knjižnje proizvodnje* [The question of the organisation of our print and book production] (Gabrič 491, Žnideršič 118). This document starts with an observation of destroyed Slovene book resources and sketches the post-war re-establishing of literature and print in its technical, organisational, and functional aspects (Žnideršič 118–19). As the priority of the immediate post-war time, the document underlines the print material needed for education, decided upon by a professional league of educators. In the document, alongside the foundation of a specialised book publisher for children, the establishment of magazines for children and youth of three different age levels is planned (119). Consequently, shortly after liberation in May, the agitprop of the League of Slovenian Youth established the publishing house Mladinska knjiga on 29 June 1945, which in September that year published the first editions of the magazines *Ciciban*, for the first four grades of elementary school children; *Pionir*, for older elementary school children; and *Mladina*, for high school youth and students. It also started an initially modest book publishing programme. Kristina Brenk, pedagogue, writer, theatre maker, and later long-term editor of children's literature at Mladinska knjiga, described the founding meeting:

The circumstances in which we found ourselves were an image of our liberated homeland in May 1945. In Styria and Upper Carniola, there were piles of ashes in school yards, where Slovene alphabet books and textbooks had been burnt, and empty shelves in school libraries. Partisans and survivors of concentration camps were returning home and disabled, lame and blind people were still sick with fear and death and empty hopes. Sixty years have passed since then. I remember a room on what was then Šempeterska Street, on the first floor above a rope factory. The meeting was initiated by Josip Ribičič, and alongside him there were two fellow-writers [...] Oskar Hudales and Albert Širok: All three of them had fled to the then Yugoslavia from Fascist occupation of the Slovene Primorje. (Štraus 12)

Josip Ribičič was himself an experienced teacher, writer, and editor, who had worked before the war as the editor of the children's magazines *Novi rod* [New kinship], published in Slovenian in Trieste from 1921 till 1926, when it was cancelled in the wake of Italian Fascist repressions, and later *Naš rod* [Our kinship] (1929–44), as well as editor of the wartime *Slovenski pionir*. For the early post-war years Ribičič was a member of the editorial boards of the magazines *Pionir* and *Ciciban*. The founding members of Mladinska knjiga already knew each other from the pre-war period from their collaboration with the magazine *Naš rod* and the publishing house Mladinska matica (Koblar). After the founding of Mladinska knjiga all of them contributed in individual ways to its programme.¹⁰

Around these professionals at Mladinska knjiga, many other writers, editors, illustrators, and cultural workers gathered. A look at the roster of the authors and artists of

the post-war magazines *Pionir* and *Ciciban* testifies to the inclusion of a broad professional network, already variously engaged with production for children before and during the war. Even many writers and painters who had not previously produced for children started contributing to these magazines.¹¹ Given the above-mentioned editorial goal of the war-time *Slovenski pionir* of providing a platform for as many as possible cultural workers, there are solid grounds for positing that it was the post-war literature for children, through its platform *modus operandi*, that substantially supported the post-war revolutionary social homogenisation of the cultural scene. That said, it must be emphasised that even in the early post-war years other styles coexisted alongside social realism. In addition, the centralised organisational structure, devoted to the implementation of the outline of the post-war publishing structures articulated in the above-mentioned war document, enabled the foundation and immediate functioning of the specialised children's publisher even amid post-war material shortages (*Ciciban* was, from its first issue on, printed in four colours and in a remarkable print run of 82,000 copies, whereas today's average print run of *Ciciban* is 12,000 copies) as well as the lack of infrastructural, institutional, and distribution networks.

Mladinska knjiga provided an essential hub for numerous actors from different fields of activities, who pooled their talents and enabled an impressive growth in production for children.¹² Thus, from the perspective of 'precarity' as a condition producing and sharpening 'precariousness', the centralised (though professionally inclusive) structure seems to have worked *against* and not *for* precarity. Also, the first post-war year's magazines had already included many contributions by children,¹³ especially in the form of short letters. As time went on there was a systematic and continuous inclusion and education of children in writing and visual expression, implemented by a coordinated effort involving the children's magazines and their open calls for contributions, hand in hand with literary and aesthetic education at schools, festivals, engaged editors, and reviewers. This all enabled not only what would today be called 'successful careers in literature for children and broader cultural field' but in particular a remarkable development of smaller and less developed literary systems, like those of Bosnia-Herzegovina, Macedonia, Montenegro, and Kosovo. By contrast, current original output from these production contexts has more or less stagnated and depends on import and translation, usually omitting the past practice of equipping translations with original illustrations produced by illustrators familiar with the context in which the translated work would appear. In the light of these considerations, the post-war centralised structure that enabled the initial post-war production again does not appear as an instrument of 'precarity' but rather as a strategy working against 'precariousness'.

Children in War and Post-War Precariousness: War Trauma and Its Overcoming

In the concluding part of this article, I want to approach the question of content, or how post-war literature addressed the generation of children who had experienced the violence and precariousness of war and were now living through the post-war reality.

The first editor of the wartime *Slovenski Pionir*, the above-quoted Mitja Vošnjak, reported on two additional wartime editorial guidelines: of political and social agitation of children and also on the objective of 'quality reading'. The Soviet model undoubtedly served not only as the template for the post-war centralised organisational structure but also in cultural-political terms regarding suitable and appropriate print content for children (Kobolt 'Negotiating the Impact'). Reportedly, Yugoslavia initially followed Maxim Gorky's 1933 'scheme' *Literaturu detiam* [Literature for children]), translated into Serbian in 1945 (Alečković). In this essay, Gorky defined the role of literature for children as a clearly

'educative' one (Gorky 6) and promoted a centralised and prescriptive paradigm (in terms of genre, content, form, and production). As the researcher of the Slovenian publishing industry Martin Žnideršič noted in his study on the influence of the state on editorial decisions from 1945 to 1990, although publishing programmes were supervised by higher agitprop ranks in the first post-war years, this practice was abandoned, especially after the abolition of agitprop in 1952 (Žnideršič 3).¹⁴ With regard to the post-war construction of the canon of Slovenian children's literature, the children's literature researcher Peter Svetina has emphasised the rupture that the revolution and its agitprop cultural and editorial policy were to cause, especially in the first post-war decade, and pointed out that the post-war selection of modern Slovenian children's literature avoided motifs and material that were typical of bourgeois and Christian culture. As I will show in the following analysis of the selected post-war periodicals, both Christian values (such as empathy and selflessness), and even some Christian motifs, and some bourgeois principles (such as the family as a social core) continued to be present, albeit within the framework of socialist ideology.

Figure 1. Ivan Miklavec, 'Otrok v internaciji' [A child in internment], cover of the magazine *Pionir*, 1945/1946.

The content of the first post-war issues of *Ciciban* and *Pionir* mostly depicted the war and post-war reality in social-realist and partly socialist-realist traits, although other styles were also represented. The illustrated content of the magazine *Pionir*, produced by the 'editorial board of Mladinska knjiga', comprised articles disseminating mostly political education, like reports on Marshal Tito, Joseph Stalin, and NOB fighters proclaimed national heroes, addresses by the minister of education, letters from pioneers, essays on youth in the Soviet Union, the role of pioneers in the new society, and so on. <FIGURE 1 NEAR HERE> In addition, each issue published original poems, usually on the war and post-war reality: 'Pioneers to Partisans', 'Pioneers Talk', 'Freedom', 'At School', 'Traitors', 'Belgrade', and similar titles reflected the politically charged content of the poems. Mostly original belles-lettres prose highlighted social topics, as in Miško Kranjec's 'Za dom' [Towards home]: a story about a group of orphans, travelling alone and without anything in their pockets from internment in Germany to reach their abandoned and ruined homes. On their way the children meet people who give them animals, making it possible, when they reach their destroyed homes, to start their young lives anew. Most of the stories promoted agency regarding reconstruction of the devastated homeland, social trust, and trust in people willing to help. The articles devoted to 'science and history' brought topics from the history of technology, agronomy, social and cultural history to biology, and promoted trust in education, science, and modernisation.

The experience of war was, especially in *Ciciban*, transmitted in various forms. For example, war violence was depicted in the rebus story 'Trije pastirčki in ptičica' [Three herders and a bird] by Josip Ribičič, illustrated by Mirko Lebez, in which some herders wonder why a bird is singing a sad song, until the bird tells them that she is sad as she knows about three small siblings who have been left completely alone and hungry, their parents having been murdered. The herders respond that they will sow wheat for the children, as they 'are not only herders but also pioneers'. The section 'Pioneers Write' featured different war experiences written by children,¹⁵ from the loss of loved family members and animals, as well as home, to jokes about fascists who stole cats to eat, but also the experiences of internment:

Internment: I was in internment. I was very hungry there. My dad was there too, but I didn't see him because the fascists wouldn't let me go to him. My mother also died in internment. How much sorrow my young heart suffered! They would not let me see her, even when she was dying. I only went to the funeral. I came back from Italy an orphan, without my mother. (Pioneer Marica Štimec)

The memory of Gonars: There was a hunger in Gonars that cannot be described. We ate all the peelings that the cooks threw into the pit. One day we all fell into that pit. I was down below; the others fell on top of me. All my bones were aching. I got some peelings. It was sad in Gonars. (Pioneer Milan Cimprič).

In the second *Ciciban* issue was a story by Utva-Ljudmila Prunk, illustrated by her daughter, illustrator and writer Ksenija Prunk. 'Pekoča bolest' [Burning pain] is a short story about two orphans, a brother and a sister, who have lost their parents in the war and do not know the location of their grave. However, their grandmother takes loving care of them and comforts them. Family values, such as loyalty to family, are promoted but also extended to a broader sociality. The distress of children whose parents had collaborated with the Nazi and Fascist occupiers was addressed in the series 'Cenček', illustrated by Mara Kralj, each episode of which thematised a social problem and invited pioneers to solve it ethically. Pioneers were supposed not to discriminate against the children of traitors, as they were not responsible for the actions of their parents and should therefore also be welcomed by the pioneers. Both magazines also introduced the topic of displaced children, mostly in the recurring character Bosanček [Bosnian], referring to children who were orphans from Bosnia-Herzegovina and the difficulties they faced during their integration into Slovenian-speaking schools and society: thus, pioneers should welcome them and be kind to them.

The magazines offered not only a space for the experiences of war violence to be narrated and heard, and so socially recognised, but also a demonstration to children that they should receive comforting support from adults. In addition, children themselves were called upon to help others, especially other children and also elderly people. Children's agency was addressed not only in social relations but also in regard to material reconstruction, from work on the reconstruction of railways to agriculture and especially in school education. In the third annual of *Ciciban* (1947/1948), there was, for example, the short story 'Igra o planu' [Play about the plan] by Josip Ribičič, illustrated by Marlenka Stupica (née Muck), who with her illustrating work for children later became one of the most acclaimed Slovene illustrators of that time. The story introduces Dom igre in dela [The house of play and work], or kindergarten, which children should visit in order not to be bored at home and instead to play and learn with other children. In the kindergarten's playground the children's play concerns a new autarkic economic plan, which they explain to a boy, a foreign industrialist's son, observing them from behind the fence. The children are building factories so they can produce everything they need independently and not need to buy things from abroad. They explain that their power plant (which the foreign boy would like to buy from them) belongs to everybody, just as everything that they create belongs to everybody, and propose he buy fruits, wine, and tobacco, which they have enough of, instead. As the children are unwilling to sell him the power plant they have built, the boy threatens not to buy their fruits any more. The children reply, singing that in that case someone else will buy fruits from them.

What kind of agency were children called up and guided to by the post-war *Ciciban* and *Pionir*? Firstly, ethical agency in relations with their peers, who had different war as well as post-war experiences, was encouraged. Understanding for different experiences and

positions of children in post-war everyday life and virtues like generosity, honesty and fairness, diligence, and tenderness were promoted. Children were portrayed as all belonging to the new society, regardless of their war experiences and origin. They were exhorted in their social agency to join and contribute to the building of the new society. As in the Soviet Union, kindergartens, schools, and Pioneer houses (*Pionirski domovi*)¹⁶ were promoted as spaces for children to meet and get help. Older children were called upon to join the workers' brigade. Smaller children were encouraged to take part in activities like theatre performances, drawing, and dancing, but also crafts that they could accomplish, from harvesting to baking bread or carpentry.

Alongside the introduction of the new political and social order, both magazines also made space for representations of children's wartime experiences, often even very violent ones. As elaborated above, according to the relational (Feldmann and Laub) but also the hermeneutic trauma model (Meretoja), the social act of discursivisation of traumatic experiences should be understood as the possibility of overcoming the trauma itself. If trauma is to be addressed and eventually overcome, it must obtain intelligible social contours and therefore it must first be narrated and acknowledged by others (Feldmann and Laub 57). Thus, in *Ciciban* and *Pionir* the 'precariousness of life' in war and in post-war times was not only addressed and given a discursive framework – a vocabulary was offered to children with which the traumatic experiences could be addressed, supported by illustrations that underlined the affective dimension of feelings of loss and the ways others were to support children in their traumatic experiences – so that the experiences of war and violence could be integrated into sociality, but the children were first and foremost called to (narrative) agency (Meretoja), which, as trauma recovery studies teaches us, is the most significant part of work towards the overcoming of traumatic experiences (Feldmann and Laub, Meretoja).

Conclusion

Examining diverse aspects of the post-war reality – political-organisational, cultural-political, structural, editorial, material, interpersonal, affective to iconographic – allows for a rereading of the immediate post-WWII revolutionary past in a complex way. Both the centralised organisational structure and the dominance of social-realist aesthetics attest without doubt to the post-war processes of political, cultural-political and institutional homogenisation. However, a closer inspection of the organisational structures, editorial decisions, and content produced reveals an inclusivity not only in terms of the professional networks engaged by the re-established children's publishing infrastructure, but also in terms of the promotion of the ethics of inclusion and agency, involving everyone, regardless of their origin, in the construction of the new society. As such, both the centralised organisational structure and the produced content can hardly be characterised as tools of 'precarity', as they obviously worked *against* and not *for* 'precariousness'. The consequent findings, that the centralised organisational structure did not intensify the post-war precariousness but rather worked against it, should also encourage methodological or rather epistemological considerations, especially with regard to the universal reliability and accuracy of concepts deduced from totalitarian studies and the implementation of these concepts vis-à-vis different revolutionary historical moments and contexts. The totalitarian dispositive, if applied uncritically, can become an operation of 'precarity' itself. Applying the concept of 'precarity' to a rethinking of the post-war and revolutionary context of socialist Yugoslavia allows at least for a certain re-scratching of the historically sedimented surface of

this historical time and production in question, which may in turn instigate an overdue discussion on how in today's times of war to address children not only concerning the 'precariousness' of war but also of its 'precarity'.

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Notes

¹ The Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia was founded and organised as a federation of six republics including two autonomous regions and politically was a one-party system; its social and economic system from the 1950s on was based on socialist self-management. The country's dissolution began in 1991 with the Yugoslav wars and subsequent introduction of multi-party systems, representative democracy, and neoliberal capitalism into the different national states of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, and Slovenia.

² Individual Yugoslav production contexts differed in accordance with the different temporalities stemming from different historical constellations of individual nations and had an impact on uneven starting and development positions of the socialist Yugoslav republics and their literatures for children.

³ Due to the lexical, syntactical, and cultural proximity of the Croatian, Serbian, Bosnian, and Montenegrin languages, the term 'common language' (embracing all four) has been introduced (cf. 'Deklaracija o zajedničkom jeziku' and Kunzmann-Müller).

⁴ For global aspects of postsocialism cf. problematisations by Fraser and Gille.

⁵ While *The Oxford Dictionary of Literary Terms* (Baldick) does not distinguish between 'socialist realism' and 'social realism', (post)Yugoslav literary studies and art history do (Dolinar). This is a consequence of the specific Yugoslav cultural history and the outcome of the discussion on realism and modernism (also known as the discussion or the conflict on the 'literary left', Lasić). 'Socialist realism' refers to 'Stalinist dogma in literature: the established techniques of 19th-century realism were to be used to represent the struggle for socialism in a positive, optimistic light, while the allegedly "decadent" techniques of modernism were to be avoided as bourgeois deviations' (Baldick 651–2). As such, socialist realism experienced only a few introductions in Yugoslavia, while social realism (with its focus on concrete and everyday social reality, particularly of peasants and workers, usually with realist-naturalistic traits [Dolinar]) marked Yugoslav literatures from the 1930s on.

⁶ The programme of the Slovenian Liberation Front (1st Congress, July 1945), for example, stated in its 12th article: 'The people's democratic power must provide the broad masses of the people with the fullest possible free education and the unhindered enlightenment development of every citizen, both in the sense of personal growth and cultural activity' (Gabrič 492).

⁷ Even though in the NOB children sometimes also took part in armed struggle, as in the Bosnian-Herzegovinian pioneer brigade Birča, which according to some sources comprised more than 600 hundred boys and girls (Idrizović 41), the organisation mostly deployed them in support roles, like couriers and similar (Vošnjak 30).

⁸ The Fascist repression had started in some parts of Yugoslavia, like Primorje in Slovenia, Istria and Dalmatia in Croatia, as early as the 1920s.

⁹ Cf. organisations like Liberation Front and Ljudska prosveta [People's Education], Zveza komunistične mladine [League of Communist Youth], Antifašistična fronta žensk [Antifascist Front of Women] as the historically largest women's movement worldwide, Zveza mladine Slovenije [League of Slovenian Youth] and so on.

¹⁰ Josip Ribičič worked at Mladinska knjiga as an editor and writer, Oskar Hudales as a writer and member of the editorial board of the magazine *Pionir*, Kristina Brenk as a writer and editor of the first selected issues and later, from 1949, as a long-standing editor and writer, and Albert Širok as a writer and editor.

¹¹ To name only some of the cultural workers who contributed to the magazines: from writers Prežihov Voranc, Miško Kranjec, France Bevk, Tone Seliškar, Utva-Ljudmila Prunk, Fran Seleški-Finžgar, and many others, to painters France Mihelič, Maksim Gaspari, Marlenka Stupica, Cita Potokar, Marija Vogelnik, Roža Piščanec, Melita Vovk Štih, Ivan Miklavec, Gvido Birolla, Ive Šubic, Marij Pregelj, France Podrekar, Tone Kralj, Nikolaj Omersa, and many others.

¹² In only two decades some Yugoslav republics (particularly Slovenia and Serbia) caught up with the European average of book production per capita, as well as established important intra-Yugoslav and international production networks (Brenk; Štraus; Žnideršič 129).

¹³ For the inclusion and participatory (infra)structures of the socialist Yugoslav literary system for children compare the article 'Literature Builds Children, Children Build Literature. Literary Education in Socialist Yugoslavia and Children's Literary Agency' (Kobolt).

¹⁴ Žnideršič identified as control mechanisms of the agitprop period selection of titles for subsidies (currently once more the practice in Slovenia, where the public book agency subsidises individual titles) and direct political pressure on directors or editors-in-chief. From 1952 on, when censorship in Yugoslavia was officially abandoned, this influence came to be exercised through personnel policy and through publishing councils, although this was no longer possible after the mid-1970s, due to the organisational modes in late self-management (Žnideršič 2, 3).

¹⁵ In 1946, the Ministry of Education issued an open call, communicated through schools, for children to submit their written and visual testimonies about their war experiences. They received over 6,000 contributions (Ribičič), a selection of which was published by Mladinska knjiga in 1948 under the title *Še pomnite tovariši. Spomini slovenske mladine na čas osvobodilne borbe* [You still remember, comrades: Memories of Slovenian youth during the liberation struggle].

¹⁶ After the war, the Pioneer organisation supported the extracurricular education of children substantially (Duda 40). Thus, alongside schools, Pioneer Homes were also established, where writers, artists, and cultural workers worked for and with children (Ognjanović and Prelić 216, 217).

The Author

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